

Design and experimental evaluation of a thermochemical energy storage system for mid-term energy storage

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Abstract

This paper presents the design and lab-scale testing of a thermochemical storage reactor that utilizes composite adsorbents, i.e. silica gel/CaCl₂. The development included the preparation and characterization of the storage materials and the identification of the optimal packing ratio of the reactor. The lab-scale testing was performed to evaluate the performance of the reactor and the composite adsorbent under various conditions, in terms of operating temperature and dynamic response. The results show that the reactor is capable of efficiently storing and retrieving thermal energy, with high energy storage densities and fast response times. The reactor design and performance results presented provide a valuable foundation for future work aimed at developing practical, large-scale systems for integration into the district heating network.

Keywords: thermochemical storage; composite adsorbents; district heating; monthly storage

Introduction

The use of sorption storage for mid to long-term applications is gaining interest, not only for the residential areas but also in combination with district heating and cooling (DHC). Indeed, one of the most interesting fields of application is thermal-electric sector coupling. In this case, it is possible to use sorption storages as decentralized storages at district/substation levels or even at building levels, charging them directly from the main district heating/cooling ring or in combination with heat pumps. This is especially useful in the new generation of DHC, that approach the concept of “temperature neutral” network, in which the temperature is kept as close to ambient temperature as possible. At the same time, the new generation of DHC is intended to accommodate a larger share of renewables inside the grids (thermal and electric), which requires suitable storage systems for peak shaving and load shifting.

Sorption storage allows to answer to such challenges, thanks to its high flexibility (it can be operated for heating and cooling purposes), virtually lossless operation and possibility of being installed also in residential areas or in buildings (differently from underground storage or aquifer storage). The main challenges that sorption technology has to face for the specific application are: possibility of using non-toxic materials and refrigerants, that would hinder installation in buildings; the need for high energy density and a charging temperature lower than the state-of-art application of sorption system, usually intended for charging with solar heat or industrial heat at temperatures higher than 80°C.

Starting from such basis, the complete development of a thermochemical storage for the application in DHC was carried out, starting from the selection and preparation of the composite material and the lab-scale testing to evaluate its performance in terms of response time, power output and energy storage density. Results were also used for the calibration of an existing model of the storage.

Material selection and preparation

The material selection was carried out thanks to a dedicated preparation and characterization campaign at CNR-ITAE. Initially, 3 ionic liquids, namely [emim][Ac], EMIM DEP and DMIM DMP,

and different salt hydrates, K_2CO_3 , $FeCl_2$, $LiCl$ and $CaCl_2$ were selected. Experimental tests were carried out on the pure materials using the Dynamic gravimetric vapor sorption analyzer (DVS) equipment from Surface Measurement Systems. Results from the tests, highlighted that the ionic liquids show a higher sorption capacity at lower relative pressures (up to 0.9 kg/kg for a 40°C isotherm for the DMIM DMP and up to 0.6 kg/kg considering the application in heat pump-assisted operation), but their cost is still too high for large scale application. The salt hydrates showed up to 1.6 kg/kg of sorption capacity, but the vast majority of adsorption is shifted towards higher pressures (3 to 4 kPa for the K_2CO_3 isotherm at 40°C), thus indicating that a higher charging temperature might be needed.

However, since salt hydrates showed leakage issues already during the small-scale testing, composite adsorbents using silica gel and $LiCl$ and $CaCl_2$ were prepared using the wet impregnation method. The composite prepared were tested in the DVS equipment and showed up to 0.6 kg/kg water adsorption.

Due to cost and corrosion issues, the silica gel/ $CaCl_2$ (25% wt) composites were selected for the lab-scale testing of the prototype.

Experimental testing of the lab-scale prototype

Testing facilities

The experimental testing was carried out in a testing rig dedicated to the testing of thermal systems. It includes a 36 kW electric heater connected to a 1 m³ water storage, and two air/water chillers connected to 0.75 m³ storages that act as heat sinks/sources at different temperature levels. The temperature inside the 0.75 m³ are also regulated by means of immersed heaters. Fast-response 3 way valves connected to a custom-made PID control in LabVIEW allow the continuous control of the inlet temperatures of the circuits. All circuits are thermally insulated. Temperature inlet/outlets are measured using Pt100 class 1/10 DIN sensors, temperatures inside the storage are measured using class A type T thermocouples, flow rates are measured using magnetic flow meters with ± 2.5 % full scale accuracy.

Heat exchanger preparation

The composite material prepared was used for filling a heat exchanger (HEX) with external dimensions of 266 x 132 x 445 (l x w x h) having aluminum fins and copper tubes coated with an epoxy resin to avoid possible corrosion from salt leakage. The heat exchanger was filled with a mixture of silica gel (Siogel® from Oker Chemie) and the composite, in 3 different ratios in volume: 50(siogel)-50(composite), 40(siogel)-60(composite), 30(siogel)-70(composite). As shown in Figure 1, the heat exchanger was subsequently closed by means of a metallic frame.

Figure 1: the heat exchanger with the composite material.

Testing methodology and results

The tests were carried out considering the possible operating boundaries for the system, listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Testing conditions.

CHARGE	DISCHARGE
Heat source: 85°C / Condensation: 30°C	Adsorption: 30°C / Evaporation: 15°C
Heat source: 75°C / Condensation: 30°C	Adsorption: 35°C / Evaporation: 15°C
Heat source: 85°C / Condensation: 35°C	Adsorption: 30°C / Evaporation: 10°C
Heat source: 75°C / Condensation: 35°C	Adsorption: 35°C / Evaporation: 10°C

An example of the results during the discharge of the prototype is shown in Figure 2. It is possible to notice that there is a ΔT ranging between 6 and 2 K for about 2000 s, corresponding to a power of 0.5 kW to 2.5 kW. If the system is used for contemporary cooling provision, a useful effect is also available at the evaporator.

Figure 2: results of a discharge test.

Results were also further analysed considering the achievable energy storage density in the various conditions. In the first preliminary tests carried out, up to $300 \text{ J/g}_{\text{adsorbent}}$ were achieved, which is about 30% less than the theoretical energy storage density of the material, but still represents a promising result.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this paper presents the design and initial lab-scale testing of a thermochemical storage reactor that utilizes composite adsorbents. The results show that the reactor is capable of efficiently storing and retrieving thermal energy. The study provides important insights into the potential of composite adsorbents for thermochemical energy storage and highlights the need for further efforts to get close to the theoretical energy density of the material. Overall, this work represents a significant step towards the development of sustainable and efficient energy storage solutions for the district heating sector.

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